
PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF CHILD-CENTRED EDUCATION AND ITS IMPLICATION TO BASIC EDUCATION SCHOOL SYSTEM IN NIGERIA

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Curriculum reforms in this 21st Century has been largely based on the child-centered approach of teaching and in many ways represented as the application of philosophy of education. Although Plato and Socrates, even Dewey reminded people long ago that learners were not empty vessels, blank slates, or passive observers, thus, much of Europe and America schooling today has been based on this premise: however, the reverse is the case in Nigeria Education system. Teachers have talked; students have been directed to listen is the basic philosophy of Nigeria education The new pattern of school life which is seen as child-centred education reflects a fundamental change that has been taking place in education in the last decades. Child-centred education derives from Rousseau's educational theory. The paper examines the concept child-centred education as a participatory learning environment which provides the learner with sufficient opportunities to be actively engaged in the learning process resulting from teaching. Principles of the concept were also provided in order to avoid philosophical fallacies, it includes, Respect the Pace of Development of Each Child, Zone of Proximal Development. The paper also identified Conditions Logically Necessary for The Application of The Child-Centered Education, this will provide a justification and unbiased clarification of the concepts, these include: Natural Goodness of the Child, Recognition of Existing Knowledge and Experiences of the Child. Finally, recommendations were made in line with the major findings. The recommendation made include to improve on the effective teaching and learning activities, there is need for teachers to ensure that learners are not passive in classrooms but consider interaction with the natural world (active learning). Teachers also need to be re-trained through in-service courses to improve their pedagogical skills in teaching approaches. The support may come from parents, school management, national or even county government. It is evident that teacher training will develop and equip teacher trainees with a variety of skills on the use of child-centred approaches.

KEYWORDS: PHILOSOPHICAL, ANALYSIS, CHILD-CENTRED EDUCATION, BASIC EDUCATION.

Introduction

Education is concerned with the transmission of worthwhile values such as skills, knowledge and planned activities that can develop learners' potentials for human and national development. The importance of education cannot be overemphasized; it provides opportunity for one to acquire knowledge, skills and traits for both human and national development (Anaduka, & Okafor, 2003). Education is seen as a desirable way to narrow the existing gap between members of the society who are from the affluent line and those who are suffering from poverty. Various governments and international actors are encouraging many children, including those from the poorest countries, to attend school to be assured of having a bright future ahead of them

Basic Education is fundamental to human and societal development. This is because It is the foundation upon which other levels of education are built and a necessary prerequisite for human and national development The Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme is nine (9) year basic educational programme which was launched and executed by the government and people of the federal republic of Nigeria to eradicate illiteracy, ignorance and poverty as well as stimulate and accelerate national development, political consciousness and national integration. The primary target of the UBE policy is ensuring that every Nigerian child acquires a minimum of 9 years basic education. Universal basic education comprises (9) nine-year duration comprising (6) six years of primary education and (3) three years of junior secondary education.

By inference the whole gamut of UBE is to avail learners' opportunity for intellectual development. Most strikingly is learning at the early stage, where experiential base is weak. But then, the progressivist educator would argue, this is a right point to begin. Notably J.J. Rousseau (1712-1778) argued that, true education is simply the development of the original nature of the child, education should foster the independent judgement in children so as to enable them live in harmony with their environment as well as individual differences must be given great consideration. However, the issue of the influences exacted on the learner(s) by the social, economic, and cultural milieu, remain unanswered of concern therefore, rests on the cardinal provisions of the UBE deeply in meeting the basic learning needs of the learners, (Anaduka, & Okafor 2003) opined that the emphasis of Universal Basic Education Policy is "education" rather than schooling. The UBE policy has to do with the all-round development of the child. That is, a life-long learning programme aimed at improving the literacy level of the children. The implementation of UBE programme requires adequate provision of the necessary resources such as human and material resources to cope with the increased enrolment being experienced as a result of the implementation of the programme. This is because when access to education is increased without a corresponding increase in the provision of necessary resources, quality and standards will be adversely affected.

Conceptual Clarifications of Child-Centred Education

Child-centered education has been known by variety of terms including learning-centered teaching, child centered education, child centered learning, student centered learning, child-centered approach and learner centeredness or student centered. These terms have all been used interchangeably. There have been more than forty different meanings of the term in contemporary usage (Harmelen,1998). Because these concepts are applied across all spectra/levels of education, learner-centered and student-centered tend to be the preferred terms for older learners, whereas child-centered might be used in early childhood or primary school context.

Child centered education refers to a participatory learning environment which provides the learner with sufficient opportunities to be actively engaged in the learning process resulting from teaching. Sometimes learning can take place without being deliberately taught by a teacher. In view of Dupin (2004), child-centered education is a style of instruction that is responsive, collaborative, problem-centered and democratic in which both learners and the instructor decide how, what and when learning occurs. Child-centered methods also include active learning in which learners solve problems, formulate questions of their own choice, and answer questions. Child-centered methods have repeatedly been shown to be superior to the traditional teacher-centered approach of instruction. However, child-centered methods are not intended to diminish the importance of the instructional side of classroom experience but instead; instruction is broadened to include other activities.

Child-centered education is described as a reaction to criticism of methods of teaching that emphasize transmission of information from teacher to students that involve the shift in power as driven by the need for a change in the traditional educational atmosphere where students become passive, apathetic and bored, instead child centered education give learners and demand from them a relatively high level of active control over the content and process of learning. What is learnt and how, are therefore shaped by the learners needs, capacities and interest (Schweinfurt, 2013). Child centered education echoes the idea of effective equipping of pupils with competencies in creative intelligence, critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Child-centered education places a focus on children and their learning process. It emphasizes on the needs of the learners and their capacity to initiate their own learning by choosing activities that is considered important. This is because; working independently in order to discover the learners' potential is a worthwhile educative process. However, there might be need for facilitator to work closely with such learner in order not to be dominant in the process there by working independently to discover their own potential. Any education that is not child-centered is not in fact education at all. In common with so much of educational jargon, child-centered education' has a built-in advantage for those who have a particular point of view to put forward, in as much as it seems self-evidently desirable. For who would want to deny the child himself any place at the center of the idea of education? Presumably, very few but then, if child-centered education is more or less desirable by definition, and education cannot be education unless it is child-centered there is a need to have a precise idea of what is meant by the term. In what sense is the child to be central? Fairly obviously child-centered is portmanteau phrase that might reasonably carry many different meanings for different people. But if it is going to be of any use as an ideal, it needs to have some agreement as to its meaning, and it is more than likely that the more precisely a meaning is delineated for the concept, the less self-evident is desirability of child-centered education going to be appeared.

If education is to be regarded as child-centered, then, it must at least be concerned with the advantage of the child himself. It must regard the child as an end in himself and not simply as a means to somebody else advantage. The question as to whether it is desirable that this should be the case is of course, distinct from the point that this one basic criterion for regarding an educational scheme as child-centered. But this is not the question intended to pursue here, beyond remarking that it is difficult to see how anybody could justify the intention to use some other individual merely as a means. It shall therefore assume that, in so far as child-centered education simply means that the child should be regarded as an end in him is desirable.

Principles of Child-Centered Education

Children can fully demonstrate their abilities, and their possibilities for development become the biggest, when they do something voluntarily. And good educational aims will be achieved more easily if they are based on clear principles and are linked to children's daily activities. The principles of Child-centred education can be seen below:

Respect the pace of development of each child

It seems that the crucial point in early childhood education is that it is rooted in, and also fulfills the life of, the children. It is fundamental that teachers to prepare for a variety of possible activities so that children can get started on what they are most interested in doing, and can develop that activity. In other words, children themselves decide what they do-teachers do not just introduce "activities of the day" based on detailed plans. Therefore, there will be as many curricula and timetables of activities as there are children. Teachers should keep a close watch on each child, join in their play, and assist or make an educational intervention when necessary. They should assess the development stage of each child and give assistance so that she can take a new step forward.

'Zone of Proximal Development'

Vygotsky's concept, 'Zone of Proximal Development' (ZPD) can assist the teacher to recognize individual differences in development and identify the development level of a particular child. The zone of proximal development refers to the 'possible level' that children can achieve under adult guidance. This shows the distance between the actual developmental level that children have already achieved, and the level of potential development. The teachers should act as a 'scaffold', providing the minimum support necessary for a child to succeed and take a step up to the next level. So, how can teachers identify the zone of proximal development of each child? Three points are important as pointed out by Vygotsky (1978)

: teachers' previous experiences, the child's ability to imitate, and his/her life history.

- 1. Teachers' previous experiences** help teachers to assess how they should speak to, and to what extent they should help, a child. For instance, they may think, "This boy is just like the one I took care of before. It takes some time for him to get started, but once he starts, I'm sure he can accomplish this task by himself because he has a ability to concentrate, like a boy I helped last year". Teachers can assume the zone of proximal development of the child based on such previous experience. It is better to avoid giving too many hints or instructions to a child. Drop a small hint at the beginning of a task, and change the way you speak to the child until s/he can go to the next step.
- 2. Imitation** is another aspect of the zone of proximal development. If children are able to imitate how teachers and/or peers achieve a task, they will nearly be able to complete the same task on their own. Taken together, a teacher's previous experience and a child's ability to imitate provide a stronger indication of the zone of proximal development.
- 3. Life History** helps a teacher to assess developmental potential and think about how to behave towards particular children. But do not compare one child's life history directly with that of another child. Compare a child's present situation with similar situations in their own past experience. All children can take a step forward if the teacher knows their life histories and strong/weak points, and then acts as a scaffold.

Develop child independence

Child centred educators have the following roles. Firstly, to evaluate the development level of each child, and decide how to aid and understand what he/she desires or thinks immediately. Secondly, to provide a physical and psychological environment appropriate for child development. Thirdly, to help children widen their activities and develop their ideas and the ability to think. In order to fulfill those roles, teachers should consider carefully: (1) how they provide a good environment (i.e. prepare appropriate materials so that children can develop through daily activities), (2) how they establish human relationships in the class (i.e. develop a reciprocal and cooperative relationship), (3) how they speak to children (i.e. use words and expressions appropriate for their development level and give small hints rather than give instructions).

CONDITIONS LOGICALLY NECESSARY FOR THE APPLICATION OF THE CHILD-CENTERED EDUCATION

For the concept to be considered as a child centered educational approach it has to meet the following conditions thus:

Natural Goodness of the Child

Child-centered education places a focus on the ‘whole child’, meaning that the child, conceived as a person in his own right, develops physicality, cognition and emotions. This is consistent with the idea that learning is most effective when differential development within and across physical, intellectual, emotional, and social domains is taken into account (Harmelen, 1998).ⁱ In relation to cognitive development, an individual becomes a person, implying a more complete or whole person, when he can think for himself. This implies that the child is able to make decisions and choices and to engage in critical thinking.

In this way, child centered education places an emphasis on children becoming independent thinkers. Without the body and feelings, the mind does not function and that the aim of education is to educate a child not just a mind, not just to think in certain ways but also to act in particular ways. All these aspects are considered to interact with one another. In terms of education, then, it is not only the extent and quality of children’s concrete experiences that are counted but the attitudes and dispositions that can be developed so that children can make the fullest use and sense from those experiences. Schools taking a whole child approach would ensure that the educational experiences that children gain reflect the richness and primacy of sense, perception and embodied mind, and these are viewed as fundamental in the process of learning.

Recognition of Existing Knowledge and Experiences of the Child

Learning in child centered environment emphasizes that the teachers should recognize and value each individual’s existing knowledge and experiences, from which new knowledge or understanding are built up. In view of Vygotsky educational theory each individual comes to the learning situation with prior experiences and prior knowledge, and then he builds up knowledge through his personal experiences.ⁱⁱ Therefore, experience is considered as the source of learners’ prior knowledge and prior knowledge is viewed as a bridge which helps learners to construct meaning and retain new knowledge. As such, prior knowledge and experience impacts on the capacity of the child. We can teach anything to anyone when we are able to access and take into account their prior knowledge and experience and learning is meaningful when learners can create meaning by linking new knowledge to what they

already know (Good & Brophy, 2016). According to Knowledge is authentically gained both in the classroom and beyond, so there is a need for students to build structures of recognition that accommodate and assimilate fragmented knowledge into previous acquired understanding. If new knowledge does not become integrated with their existing knowledge and understanding, learning will not occur because the new knowledge learners have acquired is fragmented and isolated. From such a perspective, teachers thereby seek to understand students' existing conceptions and design instruction that changes those conceptions in a way to achieve deep learning rather than surface learning (Weimer, 2002). This requires teachers not only to focus on children's prior experiences but also to relate to how children encounter ideas, things and other people through their experience.

Authenticity of the Character of the Child

A child-centered approach requires teaching and learning to be as authentic as possible. One of the premises of child-centered models is that: Learning is a constructive process that occurs best when what is being acquired is relevant and meaningful to the learner and when the learner is actively engaged in creating his or her own knowledge and understanding by connecting what is being learned with existing knowledge and experience. According to Lambert, and McCombs (1998), "Authentic learning occurs when children try to manipulate their environment and that children may take responsibility for their learning in an atmosphere when teachers appreciate student thinking, initiate lessons that promote cooperative learning, organize learning around primary concepts". Authentic learning, therefore, is an approach that supports students to explore, discuss, and meaningfully construct concepts and build relationships in contexts that involve real-world problems and projects relevant to learners. Teachers should thus use their knowledge of how children develop to structure learning experiences that facilitate children's learning and meet diverse learning needs with differentiated instruction (Ryan, 2005). Authentic instruction cannot take place unless teachers attend to the social and emotional aspects of learning. Teachers, therefore, should build close relationship with children, taking every opportunity to have individual conversations with them as well as the group as a whole, listening attentively to what they want to express, sharing feelings and perspectives with them and/or spending time just watching children interact with others and engage with materials. It is also important to talk informally to the child's family, from which the teacher will gain further insights about the child. In this way, teachers' interactions and behaviours help to enhance students' potential, to foster their self-esteem, to value their opinions, and to respect them.

Independence of the Learner

A child-centered approach to education also focuses on a child's independence, which implies a developmental sense of learning. In contrast to traditional didactic pedagogy, a child-centered approach emphasizes the child's independence and ability to construct knowledge.ⁱⁱⁱ When a child is supported to make a decision about what to learn and how to learn, he/she experiences a sense of independence. This fosters the ability to engage in critical thinking and use reasoning. "Critical thinking" is viewed as being key to personhood, since it aims at creating autonomous persons. Children's learning will make sense when an education helps them to think critically about the world and provides them with access to knowledge of how the world is constituted. Doddington and Hilton (2007) claimed that, "Child-centered education encourages children to become independent thinkers and when they are given opportunities to take the initiative concerning their lives".^{iv}

Learners' Autonomy and Choice

Choice is one of the central principles behind the notion of child-centeredness. Children's choice implies that they have a chance to make decisions about their learning. The way a child learns how to make decisions is by making decisions, not by following directions. If learning is a matter of following directions, students will not develop the confidence and skills to make decisions and choices in their lives. Children's capacity for choice is compromised by adult-created learning and development objectives aimed to encourage children to pursue a particular activity for the sake of their developmental progress. Providing them with choice enables them to become actively involved in deciding what kind of people they want to be and what kind of classroom or school they want to have. When teachers maximize children's experiences with choice and negotiation, children can obtain skills of decision making and the possibility to use them.^v Teachers, therefore, have to listen to the voices of children and empower them to express their views and make sense of their experiences. Schooling, ideally, is about working collaboratively with children through a partnership. Ideas for learning activities can be derived from a combination of teacher observations of an individual child's development and learning needs, while also allowing children to initiate their own learning experience. In addition, when children are afforded a right to make a choice or take the lead in their learning, this gives them more power and they learn to be responsible for their learning, therefore, child-centered approaches to education create and maintain conditions which move students toward autonomy. In other words, teachers are required to establish an environment that creates the conditions for students to develop into responsible and autonomous learners.

Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning is an umbrella term for a variety of educational approaches involving joint intellectual effort by students, or students and teachers together. Usually, students are working in groups of two or more, mutually searching for understanding, solutions, or meanings, or creating a product. Collaborative learning activities vary widely, but most center on students' exploration or application of the course material, not simply the teacher's presentation or explication of it.

Collaborative learning represents a significant shift away from the typical teacher-centered or lecture-centered milieu in classrooms. In collaborative classrooms, the teaching/listening/note-taking process may not disappear entirely, but it lives alongside other processes that are based in students' discussion and active work with the course material. Teachers who use collaborative learning approaches tend to think of themselves less as expert transmitters of knowledge to students, and more as expert designers of intellectual experiences for students-as coaches or mid-wives of a more emergent learning process. To learn new information, ideas or skills, our students have to work actively in purposeful ways. The students need to integrate new material with what they already know-or use it to reorganize what they thought they knew. In collaborative learning situations, students are not simply taking in new information or ideas. The students are creating something new with the information and ideas. These acts of intellectual processing- of constructing meaning or creating something new-are crucial to learning.

Creativity

Creativity seems to be playing an increasing part in education. The school lays special stress (by which it meant that the school should lay special stress) "on discovery", on first-hand- experiences and on opportunity for creative work^{vi}. But what precisely is meant by

“Creative”. Despite the frequency with which the term is used in educational debate, creativity remains extremely vague notion. In what sense of creative; for instance, would it be true to say we cannot deny the epithet creative to the five- year-old child who produces a picture of square cows and people with round bellied neck less mums and dads? Clearly the sense of creative as used here bears little relation to its use in the suggestion that Shakespeare can be picked out as a creative playwright or Einstein as a creative scientist.

The work is not concerned presumably with the use of the term creative in a neutral descriptive way as equivalent to productive where is nothing is implied about the quality of what is produced or the conditions under which it is produced. The concern is with the normative use of the term, that is to say with a sense of creativity, that is taken to be by definition desirable to some extent. One would not attempt to defend fairly English course as part of curriculum if one did not believe in its value in some respect. No more would people advocate creativity lesson unless it assumed that creativity is valuable in some respect. The normative sense of creative must therefore have certain condition, then what are those conditions:

One fairly obvious condition is that what the creative person reduces should be his own, if the learner offer an opinion the opinion is the learner’s opinion, if a lecturer writes a book is the lecturer’s book and if ado construct a build a house is Ado’s house. But what is meant here is that whatever is produced be it a building or an idea, must be the agent’s own in the sense that it must be the outcome of the person’s reasoning, planning or working out, it must represent his way of looking at whatever it is the person’s produces. What creative person produces cannot simply be a copy, an imitation or representation of somebody’s work. An argument or theory for example is not any own, in this sense if it simply regurgitates somebody else. To develop the spirit of creativity one has to do his own thinking and not simply parrot the thinking of others.

If the analysis of creativity given above is acceptable, then certain things follow from it. The first point is that one part of what it means to be creative scientist, artist or whatever, is that one is a good scientist, a good artist or whatever. The converse of course is not true, one may be a good mathematician without being a creative mathematician, because one may not produce any original work in mathematics. Creativity was one of the logical conditions of the child-centered education is a situation in which the learner has to be creative in any specific sphere that demands knowledge and understanding of that sphere. Any education that ignores this point is not making a realistic effort to promote creativity in various sphere.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Child-Centred education promote the idea that humans are social animals who learn best in real-life activities with others; “learning should be organized around the learners with consideration of abilities, interests in a democratic education system. The progressive pedagogies are characterized by "learning by doing a slogan which underscores real life experience as essential in learning. It also advocates much the same instructional approach as constructive learning approach does, which encourages investigation, discovery and problem solving. “Learning never meant memorization and learning does not happen by externally imposed content. Rather, memorization and other cognitive skills are the aids to learn in the process, and the starting point of all learning is the child’s common experience. Thus, Dewey, the father of child-centred education, considers education as a tool that can help learners gain knowledge from experience effectively therefore, education should not be a matter of telling and receiving, but an active and constructive process for learners.

Child-centred are preferable as it regards learner as active player in the learning process. Traditional education modeled an elitist curriculum through centuries was criticized as it aimed to classify learners. Teaching as one of the important activities in education is debatable to whether it serves self-development or only to train out people with the qualities that the society expected to be right. At the turn of the Late Nineteenth Century, a pedagogical movement called progressive education began to make great impact over the world. Progressive educators create situations that allow students to make connection to new ideas. These connections can then be developed into entirely new concepts that continue to grow throughout a student's experience. A deep understanding occurs when new information offered through higher order thinking activities prompt the learner to rethink and reshape prior idea.

Conclusively Plato and Socrates, even Dewey reminded people long ago that learners were not empty vessels, blank slates, or passive observers, thus, much of Europe and America schooling today has been based on this premise: however, the reverse is the case in Nigeria Education system. The new pattern of school life which is seen as child-centred education reflects a fundamental change that has been taking place in education in the last decades. Child-Centered education places emphasis on the person that is participating in the learning and encourages learners' empowerment, creativity and positive thinking initiative. Learner-Centered education makes learners take active role in explaining and fulfilling their learning. The teachers manipulate the various variables such as needs, interest, aptitude, motivation, intellectual ability and the quality of learning materials. The place of interest in learning cannot be underestimated. It is crucial to note that when what is taught is related to the needs of the child, the child's interest for learning is stimulated.

Based on the analysis of the concept Child-centred and for the proper usage and application of the context of Basic Education the following recommendations were made:

1. For Nigerian education to be Child-centred, the National Policy on Education has to be reviewed. It is only when this is done that the contradictions inherent in it will be identified and eliminated. Among the many contradictions, an instance will suffice. Although the National Policy on Education prescribes that it is the interest of the child that will determine his direction in education, the same policy document imposes compulsory subjects on him from primary up to the university level.
2. Teachers should be provided with training and workshop to update their knowledge regarding to child-centred approach.
3. Specialist in the area of child-centred education should encourage teachers to move away from chalk and talk teaching strategies to a more discovery-based learning with an emphasis on children's learning outcome.
4. To improve on the effective teaching and learning activities, there is need for teachers to ensure that learners are not passive in classrooms but consider interaction with the natural world (active learning).
5. Teachers also need to be re-trained through in-service courses to improve their pedagogical skills in teaching approaches. The support may come from parents, school management, national or even county government. It is evident that teacher training will develop and equip teacher trainees with a variety of skills on the use of child-centred approaches.

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